

ADAPTATION AT COP 30

KEY OUTCOMES FOR POLICY AND PRACTICE

10-12 NOVEMBER 2025, BELÉM, BRAZIL

ABSTRACT

COP30 delivered several important outcomes for adaptation, including the adoption of the Belém Adaptation Indicators, recognition of progress on National Adaptation Plans, and a renewed political signal to scale up adaptation finance. This report summarizes these developments and reflects the information gathered through documentation and exchanges during the conference. It highlights why these outcomes matter for policy and practice across different levels of governance, and how they may shape the next phase of adaptation efforts

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How to read this report

This report offers a structured overview of the main adaptation outcomes of COP30 and their relevance for policymakers, researchers, and institutions working across different governance levels.

- **Section 2** outlines the political and technical context that shaped adaptation discussions in Belém.
- **Section 3** presents the outcomes of the Global Goal on Adaptation (GGA), with particular focus on the adoption and future refinement of the 59 Belém Adaptation Indicators.
- **Section 4** summarizes the decision on National Adaptation Plans (NAPs), and the challenges countries continue to face in moving from planning to implementation.
- **Section 5** describes the adaptation-related elements of the Mutirão Package, including political signals on finance and new implementation-oriented initiatives.
- **Section 6** provides an overview of the adaptation finance landscape as context for understanding implementation barriers, including insights on the Adaptation Fund and the Baku-to-Belém Roadmap.
- **Section 7** highlights emerging risks, gaps, and priorities for the next phase of work leading to COP31 and COP32.
- **Section 8** discusses the implications of COP30 outcomes for subnational governments and the Mediterranean region, and identifies opportunities for strengthening science–policy interfaces.

Throughout the report, we emphasize the elements most relevant for subnational governments and Mediterranean regions, as well as the contributions that scientific institutions can make to support effective adaptation planning and implementation.

Table of Abbreviations

COP	Conference of the Parties
CMA	Meeting of the Parties to the Paris Agreement
SBI	Subsidiary Body for Implementation
SBSTA	Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
GGA	Global Goal on Adaptation
NAP	National Adaptation Plan
NDC	Nationally Determined Contribution
NCQG	New Collective Quantified Goal on Climate Finance
MEL	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning
LDCs	Least Developed Countries
SIDS	Small Island Developing States
IISD	International Institute for Sustainable Development
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
AGR	Adaptation Gap Report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

COP30 in Belém marked an important moment for global adaptation efforts. With climate impacts intensifying and many countries struggling to move from planning to implementation, adaptation became one of the most closely followed areas of negotiation. The conference delivered several political and technical outcomes that will influence adaptation work in the years ahead.

Key outcomes from COP30

1. Adoption of the 59 Belém Adaptation Indicators

- First shared reference point for tracking progress toward the Global Goal on Adaptation (GGA).
- Organized into seven thematic areas (water, food and agriculture, health, ecosystems, infrastructure, livelihoods, cultural heritage) and four stages of the adaptation cycle (risk assessment, planning, implementation, monitoring).
- Useful for structuring adaptation information across governance levels.
- Some indicators need clearer definitions and methodologies.
- Countries agreed to refine them through the Belém–Addis Vision, with a review scheduled before the next Global Stocktake.

2. Updated guidance on National Adaptation Plans (NAPs)

- Reaffirms key principles:
 - gender-responsive and participatory approaches,
 - Indigenous Peoples’ and local knowledge,
 - science-based planning,
 - ecosystem-based and nature-based adaptation.
- Acknowledges persistent challenges:
 - limited and unpredictable finance,
 - delays in accessing support,

- gaps in climate information (especially downscaled data),
- limited tools for assessing long-term risks.
- Independent observers highlighted additional concerns such as maladaptation risks and hard limits to adaptation emerging in vulnerable regions.

3. The Mutirão Package: political momentum for implementation

- Reinforces the focus on delivering climate action rather than expanding negotiations.
- Keeps adaptation highly visible within global climate politics.
- Encourages efforts to at least triple adaptation finance by 2035 (political signal, not an operational commitment).
- Launches the Global Implementation Accelerator to support cooperation and knowledge-sharing.

4. Adaptation finance context

- The Adaptation Fund received USD 127.9 million in pledges—far below its annual target.
- Governance issues remain unresolved, affecting predictability and direct-access pathways.
- Broader finance challenges persist:
 - insufficient amounts,
 - slow delivery,
 - limited access for subnational actors and communities.
- The Baku-to-Belém Roadmap outlines the process toward the new global climate finance goal (NCQG) to be adopted at COP31.

Why these outcomes matter for subnational governments

Subnational authorities manage many adaptation-relevant sectors and face the most immediate climate impacts. COP30 outcomes provide:

- Frameworks (indicators) that can help territories structure adaptation planning and monitoring.
- Principles to strengthen inclusion, knowledge integration, and nature-based approaches.
- Recognition of the challenges that subnational levels face worldwide—limited data, fragmented governance, and capacity gaps.

- Clearer political momentum around implementation and cooperation.

Implications for the Mediterranean region

The Mediterranean is one of the most climate-vulnerable regions globally. The outcomes of COP30 are particularly relevant because:

- Mediterranean risks—water scarcity, heat extremes, wildfires, ecosystem degradation—align directly with GGA thematic priorities.
- Structural barriers highlighted in NAP discussions (data gaps, coordination challenges) are also common across Mediterranean territories.
- Stronger monitoring and early warning systems will be essential as impacts intensify.
- Linking adaptation with biodiversity strategies is increasingly important, especially in view of CBD (Convention on Biological Diversity) COP17.
- Subnational governments play a central role in water governance, land use planning, and civil protection, making them key to regional resilience.

Overall message

COP30 delivered meaningful progress for adaptation—through indicators, updated NAP guidance, and political momentum—but major gaps remain. The coming years will require:

- Sustained technical refinement of the indicator framework,
- Improved access to reliable climate and vulnerability data,
- Stronger coordination across governance levels, and
- Increased, more predictable support so that adaptation plans translate into action on the ground.

SECTION 1 INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT

1.1. Setting the scene: Adaptation at COP30

COP30 in Belém took place at a pivotal moment for global climate policy. A decade after the adoption of the Paris Agreement, expectations were high that the conference would help shift the focus from establishing frameworks to advancing implementation, particularly on adaptation. As climate impacts intensify, many countries—especially the most vulnerable—continue to struggle with persistent gaps in finance, climate information, and institutional capacity, limiting their ability to turn adaptation plans into action.¹ These challenges created strong demand for clearer direction and greater visibility for adaptation within the negotiations.

The Brazilian Presidency framed COP30 as a “COP of implementation,” emphasizing cooperation, solidarity, and collective effort through the Mutirão Package.² This narrative was especially important in a context marked by uneven trust in multilateral processes and widening climate vulnerability.

Within this landscape, adaptation became one of the most closely watched areas of negotiation. Parties expected progress on three fronts: a usable set of indicators for the Global Goal on Adaptation (GGA); greater clarity on the persistent barriers affecting National Adaptation Plans (NAPs); and a credible political pathway to scale up adaptation finance. COP30 delivered a combination of political momentum and technical progress, while leaving several issues for future work.

This report summarizes the main adaptation outcomes of COP30, outlines their strengths and limitations, and reflects on their implications for policymakers, researchers, and subnational actors—including those working in Catalonia and across the Mediterranean region.

1.2. Why adaptation outcomes at COP30 matter for subnational governments

Although COP decisions are adopted at the global level, their implications extend directly to subnational governments, which are responsible for many adaptation-relevant sectors such as water, land use, biodiversity, infrastructure, and public health. They also operate in the territories where climate impacts are most immediate and unevenly distributed.

The adoption of the 59 Belém Adaptation Indicators helps clarify how adaptation progress can be assessed across governance levels. The decision explicitly encourages countries to reflect

¹ IIISD (2025) – COP30 Adaptation Outcomes Summary

² Mutirão Package Final Decision (Government of Brazil, COP30 Presidency)

national, subnational, and local dimensions when reporting progress.³ This strengthens the relevance of the GGA for regional and local authorities seeking to align their adaptation strategies with emerging international reference points.

The NAP decision also highlighted challenges familiar to subnational governments: limited resources, gaps in climate information, fragmented governance, and rising risks of maladaptation.⁴ These issues shape the everyday reality of adaptation planning and reinforce the importance of strong coordination between national and territorial levels. The outcome can serve as a guide for improving inclusiveness and knowledge integration in subnational adaptation plans.

Political signals from the Mutirão Package—including momentum around implementation and increased visibility for adaptation finance—provide additional context for understanding how adaptation priorities may evolve in the coming years. While operational details remain to be defined, upcoming guidance under the GGA, the Adaptation Fund, and the New Collective Quantified Goal will influence how countries and regions organize and deliver adaptation actions.

For subnational governments and the scientific institutions that support them, COP30 offers important signals and frameworks that can help strengthen territorial adaptation strategies, enhance science–policy interfaces, and prepare for the next phase of implementation.

SECTION 2 - POLITICAL AND TECHNICAL CONTEXT OF ADAPTATION NEGOTIATIONS

2.1. Expectations and geopolitical landscape

COP30 opened with strong expectations that adaptation would take a central role in the negotiations. The 10th anniversary of the Paris Agreement, escalating climate impacts, and continued underinvestment in adaptation all contributed to a heightened sense of urgency. Reports released before and during COP30 stressed that adaptation finance remains far below what is needed, limiting the ability of many countries—particularly the most vulnerable—to turn plans into implementation.¹

The COP30 Presidency positioned Belém as a “COP of implementation,” aiming to reinvigorate delivery across the Paris Agreement and foster collective political mobilization through the Mutirão Package.² This narrative emerged against a broader context of uneven trust in

³ UNFCCC CMA/2025/L.25 – Belém Adaptation Indicators

⁴ UNFCCC CMA/2025/L.24 – National Adaptation Plans (NAPs) decision

multilateralism, economic uncertainty, and global conflicts influencing the diplomatic environment.

Parties arrived expecting to advance:

- A coherent and usable set of indicators for the Global Goal on Adaptation (GGA).
- Clearer understanding of the challenges slowing National Adaptation Plan (NAP) processes; and
- A credible political signal for scaling adaptation finance.

Informal exchanges reflected both optimism and concern. Delegates acknowledged the need for renewed momentum but also noted challenges such as the clarity of some indicators after late edits, and the ongoing shortfall in meeting existing finance pledges.¹ Against this backdrop, adaptation became one of the most closely watched areas in Belém. The outcomes achieved reflect this mix of political will and necessary compromise, and highlight that further work will be required in the coming years.

2.2. Key themes influencing adaptation discussions

Across negotiation rooms, informal consultations, and exchanges with delegates, several themes consistently shaped how adaptation was discussed throughout COP30.

1. The adaptation finance gap remains a critical barrier

Parties repeatedly underlined that current levels of adaptation finance fall far short of what is needed. Delegates pointed to the unmet Glasgow goal—intended to double international public adaptation finance by 2025⁵—and noted that the new political commitment to triple adaptation finance by 2035 lacks a clear baseline or implementation pathway. Without predictable, grant-based resources, progress on adaptation will remain limited.

2. The need for practical, usable tools

Discussions on the GGA and the Belém Adaptation Indicators reflected a shared desire for tools that help countries describe and monitor adaptation progress. Concerns were raised about last-minute changes that affected clarity and measurability, with observers noting that some indicators were “rendered unusable” and would require further refinement before widespread application.¹

⁵ UNFCCC CMA/2021 - Glasgow Climate Pact (doubling adaptation finance)

3. Inclusion, knowledge integration, and equity

Delegates emphasized the importance of integrating gender-responsive approaches, Indigenous Peoples' knowledge, local knowledge, and nature-based solutions into adaptation processes. These themes align closely with the principles reaffirmed in the NAP decision⁴ and reflect growing attention to inclusion and justice within adaptation discussions. Vulnerable countries—including SIDS and LDCs—highlighted gaps in climate data, institutional capacity, and growing risks of maladaptation.

4. Tension between political ambition and technical readiness

While Parties wanted to demonstrate progress on adaptation, many of the tools and commitments under negotiation—such as indicators and finance pledges—require significant technical work to become operational. This gap between ambition and implementation shaped negotiation dynamics and will continue to influence adaptation agendas leading into COP31 and COP32.

Together, these themes form the backdrop for understanding the adaptation outcomes of COP30 and the issues that will shape the next phase of work.

2.3. The Baku high-level dialogue on adaptation

Held just before COP30, the Baku High-Level Dialogue on Adaptation brought ministers together to build political momentum for adaptation. While the Concept Note framed the Dialogue around scaling support, strengthening implementation, and promoting inclusive approaches, discussions also reflected the broader concerns countries have about the widening adaptation gap.⁶

Independent reporting on the Dialogue captured several figures raised by delegates to illustrate the scale of the challenge. These included calls for a twelvefold increase in public adaptation finance by 2025, references to long-term needs for developing countries reaching into the trillions annually, and observations that current adaptation finance flows remain around USD 26 billion¹—well below what is required. These figures were not part of the formal Dialogue conclusions but were used by Parties and observers to underline the urgency of scaling support.

Co-chaired by the COP29 and COP30 Presidencies, the Dialogue emphasized the need to keep adaptation at the center of climate action. It also reflected expectations for COP30: advancing

⁶ Baku High-Level Dialogue on Adaptation - Concept Note

the GGA indicators, improving access to finance (particularly for SIDS and LDCs), and strengthening implementation pathways at national and subnational levels.²

SECTION 3 - GLOBAL GOAL ON ADAPTATION (GGA)

3.1. Adoption of the 59 Belém adaptation indicators

At COP30, Parties adopted a set of 59 indicators to track progress toward the Global Goal on Adaptation. These indicators correspond to the adaptation targets under the UAE Framework for Global Climate Resilience and cover key sectors such as water, agriculture, health, ecosystems, infrastructure, livelihoods, and cultural heritage, as well as the stages of the adaptation cycle.⁷

Their adoption represents a politically significant step, offering countries a shared reference point for describing and organizing adaptation information. The indicator decision explicitly encourages reporting at national, subnational, and local levels, recognizing that adaptation happens across governance scales.³

However, the finalization process highlighted several technical challenges. Some indicators were modified late in the negotiations, prompting concerns from delegates and observers that clarity and usability had been compromised.¹ Independent reporting noted that certain indicators were weakened or made difficult to apply due to last-minute edits.

Parties agreed to improve the indicator framework under the Belém–Addis Vision, which will focus on clarifying definitions, refining methodologies, and providing guidance for practical use. A review is scheduled for 2028, ahead of the next Global Stocktake.³

Although voluntary and non-prescriptive, the indicators are expected to inform National Adaptation Plans, adaptation communications, transparency reports, and subnational adaptation processes. Their usefulness will depend on upcoming guidance and the availability of climate and vulnerability data.⁸

3.2. Thematic and dimensional indicators: structure and purpose

The 59 Belém Adaptation Indicators are organized into two complementary groups: **thematic indicators**, which focus on specific sectors, and **dimensional indicators**, which follow the

⁷ UNFCCC CMA/2023/16/Add.1 - UAE Framework for Global Climate Resilience

⁸ UNEP (2025) - Adaptation Gap Report (AGR)

stages of the adaptation cycle. This structure is meant to provide a broad picture of how countries are progressing in reducing climate risks and strengthening resilience.³

Thematic indicators (Targets 9a–9g)

The thematic indicators aim to measure progress in strengthening resilience across key sectors and societal domains, capturing how adaptation actions translate into improved outcomes for people and the environment:

- **Water** – reducing climate-induced water scarcity and strengthening water-related services.
- **Food and agriculture** – supporting climate-resilient production and equitable access to food.
- **Health** – reducing climate-related morbidity and mortality and ensuring resilient health services.
- **Ecosystems and biodiversity** – reducing climate impacts on ecosystems and species, and expanding ecosystem-based adaptation.
- **Infrastructure and human settlements** – increasing the resilience of infrastructure and ensuring continuity of essential services.
- **Poverty and livelihoods** – reducing climate impacts on livelihoods and strengthening social protection.
- **Cultural heritage** – protecting cultural heritage and practices from climate-related risks.

These thematic areas show that adaptation involves many sectors of society, not just the environment. The indicators help countries describe how climate impacts are changing and what is being done to strengthen resilience in each sector.

Dimensional indicators (Targets 10a–10d)

The dimensional indicators aim to track countries' progress across the key steps of the adaptation cycle in order to strengthen national climate resilience in a systematic and iterative way:

- **Risk and impact assessment** – understanding hazards, vulnerabilities, and exposure, and establishing early warning and climate information services.
- **Planning** – developing national adaptation plans and ensuring they are gender-responsive, participatory, and informed by Indigenous and local knowledge.

- **Implementation** – tracking progress in delivering planned adaptation actions and their outcomes.
- **Monitoring, evaluation and learning (MEL)** – establishing the systems needed to follow adaptation progress over time and adjust strategies accordingly.

These indicators help countries explain how far they have come in building the systems needed to plan, carry out, and track adaptation. They also show that adaptation is not only about results in each sector, but also about having the right institutions, knowledge, and learning processes in place.

A flexible structure meant for different contexts

The indicator framework explicitly acknowledges that adaptation happens at multiple levels. The text encourages countries to disaggregate indicators—where relevant—by administrative and settlement levels (national, subnational and local), geographical characteristics, social groups, and ecosystem types.³ This flexibility is meant to help countries reflect their own context and priorities, and to support subnational authorities in organizing and reporting adaptation information in a way that aligns with national systems.

SECTION 4 - NATIONAL ADAPTATION PLANS (NAPS)

At COP30, Parties adopted new guidance on National Adaptation Plans (NAPs), recognizing that many developing countries have advanced their planning efforts but still face major barriers in moving from planning to implementation.⁴ These barriers include limited access to finance, gaps in climate data, delayed support, and insufficient tools and capacity for assessing medium- and long-term climate risks.

The decision reaffirms that NAP processes should be:

- Gender-responsive and participatory,
- Transparent and informed by science,
- Guided by Indigenous Peoples' knowledge and local knowledge, and
- Make use of ecosystem-based and nature-based approaches where relevant.

These principles provide practical direction for countries strengthening their NAPs.

However, the decision also underscores several systemic constraints:

- Insufficient and unpredictable finance,
- Delays in accessing technical support,

- Gaps in climate information, especially downscaled data,
- Limited tools for analyzing long-term risks.

Countries stressed that these challenges slow down the transition from planning to action.

Independent observers raised additional concerns based on evidence and reporting: the growing risk of maladaptation and the emergence of hard limits to adaptation, especially in highly vulnerable regions.¹ Although these issues are not referenced in the decision text, they shaped broader discussions around NAP implementation.

The decision also highlights the value of:

- Integrating adaptation across national, subnational, and local planning processes; and
- Exploring synergies with biodiversity and development strategies, which remains a practical challenge for many countries.

Further work was requested from the Adaptation Committee and the Least Developed Countries Expert Group, and the next review of progress on NAPs is scheduled for 2030.

Overall, the NAP guidance adopted in Belém reinforces useful principles for more inclusive, knowledge-based planning, while acknowledging the persistent barriers that still prevent many countries from implementing their adaptation priorities.

SECTION 5 - THE MUTIRÃO PACKAGE: A POLITICAL PUSH FOR IMPLEMENTATION

For many countries — and for subnational governments in particular — the gaps highlighted in the NAP discussions reinforced the need for more predictable support and clearer pathways to implementation. The Mutirão Package, introduced by the COP30 Presidency, responded to these challenges by offering a high-level political initiative aimed at accelerating climate action across sectors and governance levels, including adaptation.²

5.1. A political signal on adaptation and finance

The Mutirão Package, introduced by the COP30 Presidency, provided a high-level political framework aimed at accelerating implementation across the Paris Agreement.² While it did not create new mechanisms or negotiated commitments, it helped keep adaptation prominently visible throughout the conference.

For adaptation, the Mutirão:

- Reaffirmed the need to scale up financial resources, especially for vulnerable countries.

- Encouraged efforts to at least triple adaptation finance by 2035—a political signal rather than an operational commitment; and
- Stressed the importance of cooperation, solidarity, and strengthening support systems for implementation.

These elements reinforced the broader message from COP30 that progress on adaptation requires not only new tools—such as the Belém Adaptation Indicators—but also predictable support to enable countries to act on them.

5.2. Supporting implementation: the Global Implementation Accelerator

The Mutirão launches the Global Implementation Accelerator, a voluntary initiative intended to support implementation of NDCs and NAPs by sharing knowledge, strengthening cooperation, and mobilizing partnerships. Although not a negotiated outcome, it responds to countries' call for stronger support systems and creates a space for collaboration among Parties and non-Party stakeholders.

Although non-negotiated, the Accelerator responds to calls from many countries for more practical and implementation-focused support. It may also create opportunities for engagement by subnational authorities and scientific institutions working on adaptation planning, climate information, and multilevel governance.

5.3. Why the Mutirão matters for adaptation

While the Mutirão does not introduce new adaptation rules or frameworks, it is important for understanding the broader political landscape in which the GGA indicators and NAP processes evolve. It contributes by:

- Emphasizing implementation over negotiation,
- Encouraging cooperation across actors and governance levels,
- Keeping adaptation finance politically visible, and
- Strengthening the narrative that adaptation must scale rapidly alongside mitigation.

For CREAL and other science–policy actors, the Mutirão provides useful context. The most substantive adaptation outcomes of COP30 remain the Belém Adaptation Indicators, the Belém–Addis Vision, and the NAP decision. The Mutirão adds political momentum around these efforts, without changing their technical content.

SECTION 6 - ADAPTATION FINANCE CONTEXT

Finance remained a central theme at COP30 because it directly influences countries' capacity to move from adaptation planning to implementation. While the COP did not produce major structural changes in the finance architecture, several developments help explain the broader context in which adaptation efforts will unfold over the coming years.

6.1. Adaptation fund: progress and governance challenges

COP30 saw renewed attention to the Adaptation Fund (AF), which continues to play an important role in supporting concrete, implementation-oriented adaptation projects. The Fund received USD 127.9 million in new pledges in Belém, but this amount remains well below its annual mobilization goal of USD 300 million, a target missed for the second consecutive year.¹ This continued shortfall illustrates the broader gap between adaptation needs and available resources.

Governance issues also remained unresolved. Parties were unable to agree on aspects related to Board composition, vacant seats, and governance norms for the Fund's transition to serving exclusively the Paris Agreement. Although these issues do not form part of the technical outcomes of COP30, they have practical implications for implementation: unresolved governance questions can delay project approvals, reduce predictability for institutions planning adaptation activities, and complicate direct access for national and subnational actors.

Despite these challenges, the Adaptation Fund remains a central instrument for project-level adaptation support, particularly for initiatives emphasizing community-based action and nature-based solutions.

6.2. The Baku-to-Belém Roadmap and the New Collective Quantified Goal (NCQG)

While not a negotiated outcome, the Baku-to-Belém Roadmap sets the political and technical process leading to the adoption of the new global climate finance goal (NCQG) at COP31.⁶ The Roadmap provides a broad timeline for structured dialogues and expert inputs throughout 2025–2026, and highlights several elements relevant for adaptation.

Two aspects are particularly notable:

- **Adaptation needs are explicitly recognized.** The Roadmap notes that the NCQG should reflect countries' vulnerabilities, gaps in NAP implementation, and the adaptation needs highlighted through national processes.

- **Political attention to scaling adaptation support.** References in Belém to tripling adaptation finance by 2035 help maintain adaptation on the political agenda, although these signals remain non-operational without an agreed baseline or pathway.

The influence of the Roadmap will depend on political dynamics leading into COP31, including differing expectations around ambition, equity, and needs-based support. Nonetheless, it frames the broader environment in which countries will plan and implement adaptation measures in the coming years.

6.3. Access and delivery challenges for adaptation finance

Across adaptation finance discussions in Belém, Parties and observers highlighted structural issues that limit countries' ability to deliver adaptation on the ground.^{1,8} These include:

- Complex and lengthy access procedures.
- Limited opportunities for national and subnational institutions to pursue direct-access modalities.
- Insufficient finance reaching local actors and communities, where much adaptation action takes place; and
- Weak alignment between available finance and the priorities identified through NAPs, risk assessments, and subnational planning.

These systemic constraints help explain why many countries continue to face difficulties in transitioning from planning to implementation. They also reinforce the importance of reliable climate information, strengthened multilevel governance, and robust monitoring systems—elements that are essential regardless of the pace of global finance reforms.

SECTION 7 – EMERGING RISKS, GAPS, AND PRIORITIES FOR COP31–32

The outcomes of COP30 advanced several key elements of the adaptation agenda, but they also highlighted areas that require continued attention in the lead-up to COP31 and COP32. These issues reflect recurring structural challenges faced by many countries, particularly those most vulnerable to climate impacts.

7.1. Operational Challenges for the GGA and NAPs

Despite the adoption of the Belém Adaptation Indicators and updated NAP guidance, countries emphasized several persistent challenges:

- Some indicators require additional clarification and methodological refinement before they can be widely applied.¹
- Many countries continue to lack locally relevant climate information and vulnerability baselines, limiting their ability to plan and report effectively.⁸
- Implementation bottlenecks—such as limited finance, weak institutional coordination, and capacity gaps—remain significant obstacles.⁴
- Aligning national and subnational adaptation processes continues to be difficult where mandates overlap or data systems are fragmented.

These challenges will shape the technical work under the Belém–Addis Vision and the next phase of NAP support.

7.2. Finance and Governance Risks

Finance discussions in Belém highlighted several structural risks:

- Repeated shortfalls in adaptation finance, including the Adaptation Fund’s recent mobilization gap, continue to affect predictability.¹
- Unresolved governance issues in key funds may delay approvals and weaken direct-access pathways for vulnerable countries.¹
- The final ambition of the New Collective Quantified Goal (NCQG) remains uncertain, with concerns that domestic political pressures may limit ambition in 2025.¹
- Delivery challenges persist, preventing finance from reaching local and community-level actors who are essential for implementation.⁸

These risks shape the broader enabling environment for adaptation but fall outside the scope of technical negotiation outcomes.

7.3. Key Priorities for Strengthening Adaptation Outcomes

Discussions across COP30, as well as reporting from observers, highlighted several priorities for the next phase of adaptation work:

- Strengthening monitoring systems and testing the Belém indicators.³
- Improving access to climate information, especially downscaled projections and integrated risk assessments.⁸
- Enhancing inclusive approaches by integrating Indigenous knowledge, local knowledge, and participatory processes.⁴

- Addressing maladaptation risks identified by independent observers.¹
- Strengthening links between adaptation and biodiversity efforts, particularly in view of ongoing preparations for CBD COP17.
- Focusing support on regions where impacts are intensifying rapidly, including the Mediterranean, where water scarcity, wildfires, ecosystem degradation, and heat-related risks are growing.

These priorities help frame the work ahead for negotiators, national governments, and subnational actors preparing for the next phase of implementation under the Paris Agreement.

WHAT STILL NEEDS WORK AFTER COP30

Despite progress in Belém, several issues require continued attention as countries prepare for COP31 and COP32.

1. Making the Belém Indicators usable

- Some indicators need clearer definitions and methodologies.
- Many countries lack the climate data needed to apply them effectively.

2. Persistent implementation barriers

- Limited finance, delayed support, and coordination gaps slow the move from planning to action.
- Subnational levels often face the strongest constraints.

3. Finance and governance uncertainties

- Adaptation Fund mobilization remains below targets.
- Governance issues could delay project approval and weaken direct-access pathways.
- Political uncertainty may influence the ambition of the NCQG.

4. Strengthening knowledge systems

- Greater integration of Indigenous and local knowledge is needed.
- Monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL) systems remain fragmented.
- Observers warn of rising maladaptation risks and emerging hard limits to adaptation.

5. Linking adaptation with other agendas

- Stronger connections with biodiversity and ecosystem resilience are needed ahead of CBD COP17.
- Nature-based and ecosystem-based approaches remain under-resourced.

6. Prioritizing regions with escalating impacts

- The Mediterranean, SIDS, LDCs, and other vulnerable regions face intensifying risks with limited adaptive capacity.

SECTION 8 - IMPLICATIONS FOR SUBNATIONAL GOVERNMENTS AND THE MEDITERRANEAN REGION

8.1. Relevance for Subnational Adaptation Efforts

The adaptation outcomes of COP30 have direct implications for subnational governments, which are often the public institutions closest to climate impacts and responsible for many of the systems covered in the Belém Adaptation Indicators—water, land use, ecosystems, infrastructure, and public health.

Three elements stand out:

1. The Belém Adaptation Indicators reinforce the importance of multi-level governance

The indicator decision explicitly recognizes that adaptation progress needs to be assessed at national, subnational, and local levels. This gives regional and local authorities clearer visibility within global frameworks and creates opportunities to align their monitoring systems with emerging international standards.

The Belém indicators can serve as a useful framework for:

- Structuring adaptation information,
- Position ongoing adaptation work within a recognized global reference,
- Identify gaps in monitoring and data systems, and
- Strengthen coherence across governance levels.

2. NAP challenges mirror subnational realities

The NAP decision also highlighted challenges that subnational governments face globally: gaps in climate information, coordination difficulties, and persistent resource and capacity constraints.⁴ These issues shape the daily realities of regional and local adaptation planning. The principles in the decision—such as gender-responsive approaches, the integration of Indigenous and local knowledge, and the use of ecosystem-based adaptation—offer practical guidance that can inform territorial strategies.

3. The Mutirão Package adds political momentum

The Mutirão's emphasis on implementation, cooperation, and scaled-up adaptation support helps reinforce the political legitimacy of adaptation at all levels. While it does not create new mechanisms, it signals that:

- Implementation barriers are now a global political priority,
- Cooperation with scientific institutions and local actors is essential,
- Multilevel coordination will matter even more in the years ahead.

For subnational governments, this provides a useful narrative backdrop for reinforcing territorial adaptation work and for seeking alignment with national processes.

8.2. Implications for the Mediterranean Region

The Mediterranean is one of the world's most climate-vulnerable regions, facing accelerated risks from water scarcity, heat extremes, wildfires, coastal impacts, ecosystem degradation, and increasing pressures on food and health systems. The outcomes of COP30 are therefore highly relevant for Mediterranean adaptation efforts, even without direct references to the region.

1. Mediterranean risks align closely with the GGA thematic priorities

The sectors most affected in the Mediterranean—water security, agriculture, ecosystems, health, and infrastructure—correspond directly to several targets in the Global Goal on Adaptation.

This alignment offers:

- Opportunities to contextualize global indicators with Mediterranean datasets,
- An evidence base to inform subnational planning,
- A clear framing for future regional cooperation.

2. The region exemplifies many of the obstacles highlighted in NAP discussions

Mediterranean adaptation challenges closely mirror those identified in Belém:

- Limited availability of downscaled climate information,
- Gaps in monitoring and evaluation systems,
- Fragmented governance across administrative levels,
- Rising risks of maladaptation, especially in land and water management,
- Increasing pressure on ecosystems that are approaching hard limits in some areas.

These dynamics reinforce the need for stronger multilevel coordination and data systems, and robust science-policy interfaces in the region.

3. The Mediterranean can benefit from global political momentum on adaptation

The call to triple adaptation finance, the focus on implementation, and the launch of global cooperation platforms (such as the Implementation Accelerator) provide opportunities to strengthen Mediterranean initiatives—particularly those connecting research, governance, and territorial adaptation.

For a region where impacts are accelerating faster than institutional capacity, momentum generated at COP30 can help raise the profile of adaptation needs and strengthen partnerships.

4. Links between adaptation and biodiversity are critical

The Mediterranean is a global biodiversity hotspot facing increasing climate pressures. Strengthening coherence between adaptation efforts and biodiversity strategies—including in the context of CBD COP17—will be essential for reducing risks of maladaptation and supporting ecosystem-based approaches.

5. Subnational authorities are central to Mediterranean resilience

Most adaptation-relevant competencies in the region—water governance, land planning, forest management, health systems, and civil protection—are held or shared by subnational governments. The Belém indicators and the updated NAP guidance provide frameworks that can support stronger, more coordinated adaptation planning at territorial scales.

REFERENCES

1. **International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD). (2025).** *COP30: Key outcomes on adaptation – Earth Negotiations Bulletin analysis*. IISD Reporting Services. <https://www.iisd.org/articles/insight/cop-30-outcome-what-it-means-and-whats-next>
2. **Government of Brazil – COP30 Presidency. (2025).** *Mutirão Package: COP30 Presidency political initiative*. Government of Brazil. <https://unfccc.int/documents/654389>
3. **UNFCCC. (2025).** *Draft decision -/CMA.7: Adoption of the Belém Adaptation Indicators (CMA/2025/L.25)*. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. <https://unfccc.int/documents/653890>
4. **UNFCCC. (2025).** *Draft decision -/CMA.7: National Adaptation Plans (CMA/2025/L.24)*. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. <https://unfccc.int/documents/653411>
5. **UNFCCC. (2023).** *UAE Framework for Global Climate Resilience (Decision 2/CMA.5) (CMA/2023/16/Add.1)*. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. <https://unfccc.int/documents/637073>
6. **UNFCCC. (2021).** *Glasgow Climate Pact (Decision 1/CMA.3)*. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. <https://unfccc.int/documents/460950>
7. **UNFCCC & COP29/COP30 Presidencies. (2025).** *Concept Note: Baku High-Level Dialogue on Adaptation*. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. <https://unfccc.int/documents/652927>
8. **United Nations Environment Programme (2025).** ADAPTATION GAP REPORT 2025: RUNNING ON EMPTY. THE WORLD IS GEARING UP FOR CLIMATE RESILIENCE — WITHOUT THE MONEY TO GET THERE [Neufeldt, H., Hammill, A., Leiter, T., Magnan, A., Watkiss, P., Bakhtiari, F., Bueno Rubial, P., Butera, B., Canales, N., Chapagain, D., Christiansen, L., Dale, T., Milford, F., Niles, K., Njuguna, L., Pauw, P., Singh, C. and Yang, G.]. Nairobi. <https://wedocs.unep.org/20.500.11822/48798>